

ω -Bromoacetoacetanilide and Its Metal Chelates^(a)

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Employing NMR technique, a bromo derivative of acetoacetanilide has been characterised to be ω -bromoacetoacetanilide. Infrared spectra of its metal chelates, $[\text{BeL}_2]$, $[\text{CuL}_2]$, $[\text{VOL}_2] \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $[\text{TiCl}_2 \cdot \text{L}_2]$ and $[\text{UO}_2 \cdot \text{L}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})]$ (where L stands for ω -bromoacetoacetanilide in the enolate form) also support the same structure.

A number of investigators have studied bromination of acetoacetanilide¹⁻⁶. Chudgar and Trivedi⁷, however, proved conclusively that the product of bromination of acetoacetanilide in acetic acid medium is ω -bromoacetoacetanilide. To confirm the structure they also cyclised the compound to obtain 4-bromomethylcarbostyryl. In view of our interest in metal chelates of the substituted acetoacetanilides, we have further characterised ω -bromoacetoacetanilide employing NMR technique and prepared its chelates with beryllium(II), a copper(II), titanium(IV) vanadium(IV) and uranium(VI).

Experimental

Preparation of ω -bromoacetoacetanilide:

ω -Bromoacetoacetanilide was prepared as reported⁷.

Preparation of chelates:

Bis(ω -bromoacetoacetanilidato) copper(II): Dried metallic sodium chips (0.46g; 0.02 mole) were added to a solution of ω -bromoacetoacetanilide (5g; 0.02 mole) in cold methanol (150 ml). When the reaction subsided, the contents were warmed and a solution of copper(II) acetate hydrate (1.99 g; 0.01 mole) in hot methanol (40 ml) was added while stirring. The complex which crystallised on cooling was filtered, washed successively with water and alcohol and recrystallised.

Oxobis(ω -bromoacetoacetanilidato) vanadium(IV): Prepared as above using a solution of oxovanadium(IV) sulphate pentahydrate (2.53 g; 0.01 mole) in hot water (20 ml).

Dioxoaquabis(ω -bromoacetoacetanilidato) uranium(VI): An aqueous solution (100ml) of dioxouranium(VI) acetate dihydrate (4.24 g; 0.01 mole) was added to an alcoholic solution (100 ml) of the bromoacetoacetanilide (5 g; 0.02 mole) and stirred for 2 hr. The precipitated complex was filtered, washed with alcohol and recrystallised.

The chelates of beryllium(II) and titanium(IV) were prepared employing modified methods used for the syntheses of the corresponding acetoacetanilide chelates^{8,9}.

Infrared spectra of mulls in Nujol were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 137 spectrometer. NMR spectrum was recorded on a Varian A 60 D spectrometer.

Results and Discussions

β -ketoamides exhibit keto-enol tautomerism in solution^{10,11}. In DMSO- d_6 , however, only four ¹H NMR signals were observed, showing that the enol form was negligible in the medium, for this simplified spectrum exclusively corresponds to that of the keto form. The signals are at 0.80 τ (singlet for -NH-), 2.80 τ (multiplet for -C₆H₅), 5.75 τ (singlet for -CH₂Br) and 6.20 τ (singlet for -CH₂-). The integrated intensities correspond with the number of protons of each type.

Infrared spectrum of the compound shows two strong bands at 1725 and 1652 cm^{-1} for the bromoacetyl and the amide carbonyls respectively. In all its metal chelates (Table 1) these bands are shifted to about 1580 and 1600 cm^{-1} respectively (Table 2), showing¹² that both the oxygens of the ligand are bonded.

The broad N-H stretching band of the ligand around 3250 cm^{-1} is shifted upwards to $\approx 3320 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the complexes. This shift indicates absence of nitrogen coordination^{13,14}.

Metal-ligand bonds in the complexes^{9,14,15} are, therefore, depicted as in Figure 1.

Fig. 1

All the metal chelates show a medium intensity band at 1195 cm^{-1} , assignable to $>\text{C}-\text{H}$ in the plane bending vibration^{8,16,17}. The presence of this band is an

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TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA AND OTHER DETAILS OF ω -BROMOACETOACETANILIDE AND ITS METAL CHELATES

Sl. no.	Compound	Solvent from which recrystallised	Yield (%)	Colour	m.p. (°C)	Analytical Data [‡]		
						C (%)	H (%)	N (%)
1	ω -Bromoacetoacetanilide (LH)	Alcohol	80	Colourless	134	47.20 (46.88)	4.17 (3.90)	5.25 (5.47)
2	[BeL ₂]	-do-	76	-do-	206-7	46.05 (46.24)	4.14 (3.85)	4.38 (5.38)
3	[CuL ₂]	Acetone	60	Green	147	42.60 (41.84)	4.06 (3.48)	4.78 (4.89)
4	[TiCl ₃ L ₃]	×	55	Reddish brown	**	(38.60 38.16)	3.74 (3.18)	3.65 (4.45)
5	[VO ₂]-4H ₂ O	*	50	Greenish black	**	38.05 (37.56)	3.95 (4.06)	3.72 (4.38)
6	[UO ₂ L ₂ (H ₂ O)]	Acetone	73	Red	198-200d	31.25 (30.00)	3.26 (2.75)	2.94 (3.51)

* Percentages found are noted first followed by calculated percentages in brackets. d. Decomposes.

** Not melting or visibly decomposing upto 360°

* Insoluble in common organic solvents, hence only washed repeatedly with warm solvents. × Though soluble in alcohol and methanol the complex decomposed in solution on standing. Hence only washed with cold and hot benzene.

TABLE 2—I. R. ABSORPTION FREQUENCIES (CM⁻¹) OF METAL CHELATES OF ω -BROMOACETOACETANILIDE IN THE REGION 1750—1540 cm⁻¹.

Be	Absorption ^(a) for chelates of				Assignments ^b
	Cu	Ti	V	U	
1603	1603	1603	1600	1603	Perturbed Amide I Frequency plus aromatic C=C skeletal vibration frequency
1578	1580	1578	1578	1575	Perturbed carbonyl frequency plus another aromatic C=C skeletal vibration frequency.
1554	1552	1553	1550	1540	Amide II frequency.

(a) All absorptions are strong.

evidence for the ligand molecule being ω -bromo- and not α -bromo-acetoacetanilide. Two strong bands at about 700 and 750 cm^{-1} (aromatic monosubstitution) are observed in the spectra of the ligand and its metal chelates.

β -Dicarbonyls react with titanium tetrachloride yielding complexes of the type prepared in this investigation^{18,19,20}. Attempts to prepare $[\text{TiCl}_2\text{L}_3]$ from $[\text{TiCl}_2\text{L}_2]$ by refluxing with excess of the ligand²¹, or by ligand exchange⁹ were unsuccessful. This is probably due to the decreased donor strength of the ligand resulting from bromine substitution.

The I. R. spectrum of the vanadyl complex shows a broad band in the 3650-3400 cm^{-1} region as may be expected for water of hydration¹³. Weak bands observed at about 3480 cm^{-1} in the I.R. spectrum of the uranyl complex are attributed to coordinated water^{22,24}. Similar aqua complexes of uranyl with β -diketone ligands have been reported²²⁻²⁴.

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